

Determinants of Inclusive Tourism in Borobudur Temple

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ABSTRACT: Inclusive tourism has gained increasing attention as a means to provide accessible and enriching experiences for diverse groups of visitors. This study aims to identify the determinants of inclusive tourism in Borobudur Temple, a renowned Buddhist heritage site in Indonesia, using a mixed-methods approach. The research integrates qualitative and quantitative methods, employing descriptive analysis, a survey with 305 respondents, validity and reliability assessments, as well as confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and exploratory factor analysis (EFA) conducted with SPSS and JASP tools. The qualitative phase involves in-depth interviews and focus group discussions with various stakeholders. Following the qualitative phase, a survey is conducted to quantitatively measure the identified determinants of inclusive tourism. A structured questionnaire is administered to 305 visitors to Borobudur Temple, incorporating Likert-scale items related to the identified themes. Descriptive analysis is used to summarize the responses and provide an overview of visitors' perceptions of inclusive tourism. The validity is assessed through content validity, ensuring the questionnaire items adequately represent the construct of inclusive tourism. Reliability is evaluated using internal consistency measures, such as Cronbach's alpha, to examine the consistency and stability of the questionnaire's items. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is conducted to test the measurement model and assess the fit between the data and the proposed theoretical framework. Additionally, exploratory factor analysis (EFA) is employed to explore the underlying factor structure of the determinants of inclusive tourism, further refining the measurement model and identifying potential new factors or dimensions. Additionally, exploratory factor analysis (EFA) is employed to explore the underlying factor structure of the determinants of inclusive tourism, further refining the measurement model and identifying potential new factors or dimensions.

KEYWORDS: Inclusive Tourism, Borobudur Temple, Accessible Facilities, In Depth Interview, Marginalized People.

INTRODUCTION

The tourism sector is a crucial aspect of a country's economy, driving the economic sector the fastest. The World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) reports that international tourism arrivals have increased from 957 million in 2010 to 1465 million in 2019. Despite a significant decrease in 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the number is expected to rise in 2021 and 2022. The UNWTO World Tourism Barometer report predicts global tourist arrivals to climb by 3% to 4% in 2020. The majority of sporting and cultural events, such as the Olympics in Tokyo and Expo 2020 in Dubai, are predicted to benefit the tourism industry. Furthermore, foreign entry rates in the European and American regions grew by 199% and 97%, respectively, compared to 2021. However, these percentages are much lower than pre-pandemic overseas arrival rates. The Middle East and Africa experienced improvements in January 2022, while Asia Pacific expanded by 44% between 2019 and 2021. After a dip in 2020 and 2021, foreign tourism is expected to gradually return in 2022. The COVID-19 pandemic has severely disrupted the tourism industry, causing social restrictions, lockdowns, and travel restrictions. The pandemic reduced international tourist visits by 72% in 2020 and 71% in 2021, resulting in a loss of 2.1 billion international arrivals. This led to a combined loss of US\$ 2.1 trillion during the two-year period. Despite these losses, several countries are attempting to recover their respective tourism industries. Europe is the leader in terms of international tourism, reaching 81% of the pre-pandemic level. The Middle East saw international arrivals more than triple year-over-year in January-September 2022, up to 71% from 2019 levels. Africa and the Americas reached 63% and 66% of 2019 levels, respectively.

Asia and the Pacific experienced an increase in arrivals in the first nine months of 2022, reflecting the opening of many destinations. The UNWTO conducted a survey to identify factors that hindered the recovery of the tourism industry in a country, including the economic environment and economic conditions. The survey found that the economic environment in various countries has been shaken by the Covid-19 pandemic, which has led to increased costs for healthcare and vaccine production. The cost of transportation is another factor in the recovery of international tourism, followed by travel restrictions and the war between Russia and Ukraine. Indonesia's tourism sector is a driving force for the country's economy and job creation for foreign tourists. In 2019, tourism

contributed IDR 280 trillion in foreign exchange, a 3.7% increase over the previous year's total of around IDR 270 trillion. The Creative Economy sector, which remains dominant, generated IDR 1.153 trillion in revenue in 2019. The Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy predicts that Indonesia's tourism sector will generate US\$1.7 billion in foreign exchange by 2022. The increase in tourism foreign exchange is linked to the increase in foreign tourist arrivals as the Covid-19 pandemic faded. The UNWTO World Tourism Barometer report predicts that global tourist arrivals are predicted to climb by 3% to 4% in 2020. Despite the pandemic, the tourism industry has been hit the hardest, causing social restrictions, lockdowns, and travel restrictions. The COVID-19 pandemic reduced international tourist visits by 72% in 2020 and 71% in 2021, resulting in a loss of 2.1 billion international arrivals. However, several countries are trying to recover their respective tourism industries, with Europe leading the way in terms of international tourism, the Middle East experiencing more than triple international arrivals, Africa and the Americas reaching 63% and 66% of 2019 levels, and Asia and the Pacific (+230%) experiencing more than triple arrivals.

BUSINESS ISSUES

I. The tourism industry in Indonesia has experienced significant growth, with international tourism increasing from 250 million people in 1950 to over 1.3 billion people in 2017. The UNWTO predicts a 3.3% annual growth rate, reaching over 1.8 billion visitors by 2030. Borobudur Temple, a well-known tourist attraction in Indonesia, is a top destination for increasing visitor numbers, with 3,855,285 visitors in 2018. The temple hosts various national and international events, such as the Borobudur Marathon and music concerts like Borobudur Night and Symphony. Inclusive tourism is crucial for ensuring accessibility for all people, regardless of their physical, economic, or social circumstances. This research aims to analyze whether Borobudur is an inclusive tourist spot, as it is essential for providing opportunities for people with limited mobility and ensuring no obstacles. The economic environment and economic conditions of a country have hindered the recovery of the tourism industry, with travel restrictions and the war between Russia and Ukraine being the main factors. The tourism sector in Indonesia is a driving force for the country's economy and job creation for foreign tourists. In 2019, tourism contributed IDR 280 trillion in foreign exchange, a 3.7% increase over the previous year's total of around IDR 270 trillion. The Creative Economy sector, which remains dominant, generated IDR 1.153 trillion in revenue in 2019. In conclusion, the tourism industry in Indonesia is a complex and dynamic with a complex regulatory mechanism. The Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy predicts that foreign exchange earnings from Indonesia's tourism sector will reach \$4.26 billion by 2022, a three-fold increase from the previous year's target. The tourism industry in Indonesia is expected to generate US\$1.7 billion in foreign exchange by 2022, driven by the increase in foreign tourist arrivals and the COVID-19 pandemic's decline. The UNWTO World Tourism Barometer report predicts global tourist arrivals to climb by 3% to 4% in 2020, with 47% of participants expecting tourism to perform better in 2019 and 43% expecting it to perform the same. The bulk of sporting and cultural events, such as the Olympics in Tokyo and Expo 2020 in Dubai, are predicted to benefit the tourism industry. However, foreign entry rates in the European and American regions grew by 199% and 97%, respectively, compared to 2021. However, these percentages are much lower than pre-pandemic overseas arrival rates. The Middle East and Africa experienced improvements in January 2022, while Asia Pacific expanded by 44% between 2019 and 2021. Foreign tourism is expected to gradually return in 2022, with some countries eliminating or reducing travel restrictions for overseas travelers. According [1] the number of persons with disabilities in Indonesia reaches 11,580,117 people when compared to the current total population of Indonesian people, namely 275,777,000 according to data from [2]. The government must therefore support inclusiveness for the tourism industry, such as accessibility for all tourism facilities and services. Inclusionary tourism is not only concerned with human rights. However, it is an opportunity for tourist destinations and governments to increase their income by welcoming all tourists. In addition, inclusive tourism is a means of achieving Sustainable Development Goal 11 (SDG 11), which is to create safe, inclusive, and sustainable cities and settlements.

[3] Consideration for the rights of individuals with disabilities is a crucial component of national development planning. In line with Government Regulation No. 70 of 2019, a Master Plan for Persons with Disabilities (RIPD) has therefore been developed. RIPD focuses the mandate of Law (UU) No. 8 of 2016 regarding Persons with Disabilities through seven strategic objectives to be attained to ensure inclusive development for persons with disabilities. Similarly to other people working in the tourism industry, individuals with disabilities must have the same rights to enjoy and participate in the tourism industry.

METHODOLOGY

Based on the objectives to be achieved, this research is included begins with problem identification, followed by a comprehensive literature review, and concludes with data collection and analysis, leading to the formulation of conclusions and recommendations. The current study will use both qualitative and quantitative research methods to complete its objectives. The study uses a qualitative methodology to identify the significant factors of inclusive tourism. This approach involves conducting in-depth interviews with visitors and tourists to gather authentic responses. Research interview conducted in Borobudur aimed to understand the proportion of visitors and tourists, including pregnant women, from disabled, elderly, and pregnant women. Researchers conducted surveys to determine the appropriate age range for participants. The data will be tested and analysed using a quantitative method using SPSS and JASP software to what important factors that detemind inclusive in Borobuur temple. The sample size for this research is 300 respondents. The method that is used to take the sample simple random sampling method for its collection of data. At the beginning of the questionnaire respondents were asked for personal data such as gender, age, domicile, and have been to the Borobudur temple before or not from provinces as well as islands. The questionnaire will be using a likert scale with 5 levels of interval. Validity is one of the tests to find out whether the measuring instrument is used for the variables in the study. The validity examination was promptly distributed to 305 respondents requesting their responses. Required for tourists and prospective visitors to Borobudur. In order for the researchers to determine whether or not the respondents in this study were consistent, they examined the reliability of the test using Cronbach's Alpha by SPPS. The reliability results that are presented in the table that is mentioned above, it is clear that the findings can be relied upon. Therefore, the responses to the questionnaire provide some fairly reliable information. In the method of factor analysis known as exploratory factor analysis or principal component analysis multiple factors will be produced in the form of latent variables that cannot be established before the study is carried out, in this research In the method of factor analysis known as exploratory factor analysis or principal component analysis (PCA = principal component analysis), multiple factors will be produced in the form of latent variables that cannot be established before the study is carried out. The fundamental concept of confirmatory factor analysis is a multivariate analysis based on relationships or correlations between variables; variables with a high correlation will generate a pattern or a new factor; one of the methods in factor analysis is confirmatory factor analysis or CFA test.

Table 1. Variable and question for questionnaire (Author, 2023)

No	Variable	Label	Indicator
1	Intention to visit	IV1	I intend to visit the Borobudur Temple tour in the next 12 months
		IV2	I am more interested in visiting Borobudur Temple tourist destinations compared to other destinations
		IV3	I intend to recommend Borobudur Temple tours to relatives to visit
2	Services and price	SP1	The services available at Borobudur Temple Tourism are in accordance with the needs and desires of tourists
		SP2	There are staff or security who guide and guide tourists in the Borobudur Temple Tourism environment such as showing directions and places
		SP3	Borobudur Temple staff can understand the specific needs of tourists
		SP4	Tourist transportation drivers can understand the specific needs of tourists
		SP5	The entrance ticket price for the Borobudur Temple tour is affordable for everyone
		SP6	Hotel prices around Borobudur Temple tours are affordable for everyone
		SP7	Lodging prices around Borobudur Temple tours are affordable for everyone
		SP8	Restaurant prices around Borobudur Temple tours are affordable for everyone
3	Social media, website & Information centers	SWI1	Access to information about Borobudur Temple can be accessed through social media and websites
		SWI2	The authenticity and appropriateness of the information displayed on both social media and the Borobudur Temple website is very accurate
		SWI3	The information center at the Borobudur Temple tour functions well and provides clear information
		SWI4	The floor plan on the Borobudur Temple tour provides a detailed description
		SWI5	The floor plan on the Borobudur Temple tour makes it easy to read it

4	Design & features facilities	DF1	There are easy facilities for climbing the tourist area of Borobudur Temple for the elderly
		DF2	Easy facilities are available to climb the Borobudur Temple tourist area for pregnant women
		DF3	There is a ramp to make it easier for wheelchair users to climb Borobudur Temple
		DF4	Toilets in the tourist area of Borobudur Temple can be accessed properly
		DF5	The prayer room in the tourist area of Borobudur Temple can be accessed properly
		DF6	Temporary resting places in the tourist area of Borobudur Temple can be accessed properly
5	Risk management & emergency response	RE1	Security in the Borobudur Temple tour is very well coordinated
		RE2	The number of existing security officers is sufficient to serve in the Borobudur Temple area
		RE3	Security facilities such as an ambulance are available in the Borobudur Temple area
		RE4	Security facilities such as firehydrants are available in the Borobudur Temple area
		RE5	Security facilities such as CCTV are available in the Borobudur Temple area
6	Tour operator & education and training	TET1	The Tour Guide provides a good and interesting explanation of the history of Borobudur Temple to tourists
		TET2	Tour Operators (Travel Bureau & Travel Agency) provide services according to the special needs of each tourist
		TET3	Information about Tour Operators can be accessed easily through social media and websites
7	Accessible Mobilization	AM1	There are vehicles that tourists can use to get around Borobudur Temple
		AM2	Hotels around Borobudur Temple are easy to access and reach by tourists
		AM3	Lodging around Borobudur Temple is easily accessible and reachable by tourists
		AM4	Restaurants around Borobudur Temple are easy to access and reach by tourists
		AM5	Easily accessible parking and close distance to Borobudur Temple
8	Accommodations	A1	There is public transportation such as the City Bus that can be used by tourists from Yogyakarta to Borobudur Temple in Magelang
		A2	There is public transportation such as the train that tourists can use from Yogyakarta to Borobudur Temple in Magelang
		A3	There is transportation such as online taxi/taxi that tourists can use from Yogyakarta to Borobudur Temple, Magelang
		A4	There is transportation such as a shuttle that tourists can use from Yogyakarta to Borobudur Temple in Magelang
		A5	There is an airplane route to the tourist attractions of Borobudur Temple
		A6	The service from public transportation is very good and understands the needs of each tourist
9	Developing policies, regulations and collaboration from the government	DRC1	Current government regulations have made the management of Borobudur Temple better and more developed
		DRC2	There is collaboration between the management of Borobudur Temple and the local community
		DRC3	The government and Borobudur Temple tourism managers create programs/activities that involve the general public
		DRC4	The government and Borobudur Temple tourism managers provide facilities to provide feedback such as input and suggestions to the general public

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Interview Result

Variable	Sub-Variable	Description	Quotation
Intention to Visit	Facility Management	Behavioral intention can be understood as an individual's attitude, response tendency, or desire toward an object; more specifically, it is the likelihood that an individual will take some action or make a choice. [4]	“tourism is very important because people with disabilities also need refreshing to tourist attractions and it's rare that tourist attractions can be accessed by people with disabilities, even though there might be only one or maybe those that can be accessed by people with disabilities “Dian hastiwi, 39
Service and Price	Training Staff	[5]a service is any action or activity that one party can give to another party that isn't tangible and doesn't lead to ownership	“like having a tour guide who guides you, directs well, or the drivers or assistants who are equipped with knowledge, like how do we accompany friends with disabilities, or pregnant women? I hope there is transportation that can facilitate such a service,” Aris Wahyudi, 36
Social media, website and Information centers	Provide Information	Website marketing and social media involve customers directly or indirectly to boost awareness, image, product sales, and service, according to Kotler & Armstrong, In [5] the tourism information center (TIC) is an asset for those planning a trip to a particular destination. For a tourism location to succeed, TIC must be available because it facilitates communication between visitors (tourists) and firms (hosts/managers) and amongst visitors themselves	“Information about the temple especially those that can be accessed via a link or the website that is open, it's just a map placed in front” Dian Hastiwi, 39
Design & Features facilities	Infrastructure	In [6] The development of the tourism sector is supported in a significant way by organized infrastructure and facilities. Tourists are able to enjoy themselves in a destination if it has the facilities and services that they desire.	“going up the stairs but it's a waste I'm old, when I went to Bukittinggi yesterday I could go up and down, now I'm not strong enough” Aisyah, 67
Risk Management and Emergency Response	Security Management	According to Dorfman and Cather in [7] risk is the chance of getting hurt or losing something. Based on the probability, risk is a shift in the amount of good or bad outcomes that can come from an uncertain event. Risk management is the process of discovering and taking care of an organization's risks so that they match its objectives.	“security, I don't understand it's just that as soon as we enter the parking lot, we are in a dilemma, street vendors are forced to buy this, buy that, we also understand that, but yeah, it's better to coordinate better” Suratman,75

Tour operator and Education and training	Tour Operator for Disability	Tour operators are a key link between tourists and destinations. This makes them a good place to start a movement toward sustainability.	it's very important to have a Tour Operator special for disability, because maybe the tour operator can be interpreted, they can convey them for disabilities, it's like they help people in wheelchairs, right? backwards, so that the wheelchair does not go down first, it needs special handling.” Dian hastiwi, 39
Accessible Mobilization	Provide Vehicle	According to Bocarejo and Oviedo in [8] accessibility can be understood as “the ease of reaching desired destinations given a number of available opportunities and intrinsic impedance to the resources used to travel from the origin to the destination	“because I'm a nuisance, I get tired easily, maybe like before, maybe there is a vehicle from the parking lot that can take me, I'm easily tired and tired so it's easy to rest or what, so maybe that, a vehicle that can take around the temple isn't all a disturbance can go around” Isti Rahayu, 29
Accommodations	Public Transportation	In [9] stated more than two fifths of tourist daily expenditures are allocated to the accommodation sector, making it the most important sector in the tourism business.	“it's still the same bro, I'm taking a private vehicle, i can't take public transportation, cause i can't get on and off the bus” kartono, 21
Developing policies, regulations and Collaboration from the Government	Collaborate event and discussion	The Policy Monitoring and Research Center says that government policies can be utilized to define every action that is aimed at improving a situation. Policy is where the government initiates when it wants to do something to make a change in real life.	“I think it's important to collaborate with the management and the government, like us, we also have a community, like the three-wheeled motorbike community, it's also rich in a combination of Magelang and Jogja, but that's not from the government community but from the community itself, so I think it's important” Dian Hastiwi, 39

From the results of the CFA analysis above, it can be concluded that the question items that have been tested have compatibility with the data and question items that have been made, so that the 5 new factors formed from the results of the analysis can be used as a measure for the inclusiveness of Borobudur temple tourism, namely:

- Management of staff, facilities, and information
- Accessible Tour Operator, accommodation, Transportation
- Accessible Facilities
- Affordable accommodation
- Transportation provided by the government

The five factors above are expected to become measurement variables for other tourism inclusiveness.

CONCLUSION

To summarize, the concept of inclusive tourism is a concept where all tourists, regardless of their physical abilities or background, such as cultural, racial, and financial backgrounds, etc. they can still enjoy tourism freely and equally with other people, however Inclusive tourism is a concept that aims to provide equal access and opportunities for all individuals, regardless of their abilities, background or specific needs. This concept focuses on creating an inclusive and welcoming environment that enables everyone to participate in tourism activities, enjoy attractions, and have meaningful travel experiences. Based on the findings, five factors form the basis for determining or measuring tourism based on research carried out at the Borobudur temple.

RECOMMENDATION

A. For Managerial Implication

Suggestion for PT TWC as the management of Borobudur temple tourism to pay attention to some of the issues above, especially in the facilities and employees, and to educate them about inclusion and how to handle each tourist's special requirements. Disability awareness, inclusive customer service, effective communication, and cultural sensitivity training for PT TWC personnel. Train staff to help disabled tourists and give accessible temple information. Create user-friendly websites and mobile apps with detailed information about temples, accessibility, transportation, and surrounding accommodation. Promote inclusive tourism at Borobudur Temple with disability organizations, local communities, tourism agents, and hotels. Include disabled people and advocacy groups in decision-making processes

B. For The Government Implication

The government should provide suitable and helpful access for tourists, especially those with special needs, and adopt a strategy on Develop and implement inclusive tourism policies and guidelines that prioritize accessibility and social inclusion in tourism planning and development, working with government agencies, disability organizations, and tourism stakeholders to meet visitors' diverse needs. Improve Borobudur Temple and associated infrastructure accessible using special funding. Establish a funding source or payment plan to help tourism businesses and operators improve accessibility. Accessibility improvements at Borobudur Temple. Install ramps, handrails, accessible paths, and toilets. provide city buses, transportation systems, airport access, rail links, etc. Create public awareness efforts to promote inclusive tourism and accessibility at Borobudur Temple. Tourism websites, social media, and events should promote Borobudur Temple as an inclusive destination.

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